

INSPECTION, CHARACTERIZATION AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF TIMBER ROOF TRUSSES: A CASE STUDY IN URUGUAY

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Abstract

Introduction:

Maintenance is an essential task to extend the service life of buildings; and yet, not well attended in Uruguay. This fact has led to the development of timber structures with assorted problems related to humidity. The warehouse presented in this paper was built at the beginning of the 20th century. Its roof is supported by trusses, made of sawn timber pieces joined by traditional wood-working joints. Due to some roof leaks and a reform project that modified the structural loads, the owners requested us a roof inspection and rehabilitation proposal. To fulfill this, we set three objectives: first, to inspect the trusses; second, to characterize the timber —since no records of the original project were founded—; and third, to analyze the structure with the new loads.

Developments:

We started visually inspecting the trusses to detect the damage caused by biotic agents and to propose its reparation. Then, we estimated the timber mechanical properties destructively (by longitudinal compression tests of small-scale wood specimens) and non-destructively (by wave propagation testing techniques). Finally, we analyzed and checked the trusses in both the ultimate and serviceability limit states, after placing the projected new covering.

Remarks and Conclusion:

Since some of the encounters between the trusses and the walls showed active attacks of fungal rot (brown rot), we recommended the elimination of the damaged areas and the reinforcement of the corresponding joints. Based on the destructive and non-destructive tests, we estimated the mechanical properties of the timber to be those of a C24 strength class —though denser (610 kg/m³). Regarding the structural analysis, we observed that the new roof covering (new loads configuration) and the stresses fluctuation due to suction wind could critically affect the structural behavior of both the woodworking joints and the trusses elements.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Uruguay has experienced a substantial advance in the framework of timber structures. As a result of a forest policy program started in the 1990s, the country has one million hectares of fast-growing species, mainly pines and eucalyptus [1]. Two years ago, in 2017, diverse sectors related to the construction of timber structures formed a Uruguayan standardization committee (UNIT) focused on timber structures. Since its creation, UNIT has approved two standards: UNIT 1261 [2] and UNIT 1262 [3], both focused on the visual grading of sawn timber of pine (*Pinus elliotti* and *Pinus taeda*) and eucalyptus (*Eucalyptus grandis*), respectively. In addition, and for the first time, some manufacturer companies have gained interest in the fabrication of engineered wood products, such as glued-laminated timber and cross-laminated timber. This advance has been accompanied, if not guided, by an increasing participation of the local universities.

However, this was not always the prevailing reality of a more distant past. Some years ago, the country did not have locally produced sawn timber, there were no companies capable of manufacturing engineered wood products, and there was no national regulation or any document that prescribed how to adapt the international standards. Even universities did not properly instruct architects and engineers on how to design and build timber structures. Under these conditions, the Uruguayan designers resorted to two practices: importing timber from other countries —such as Brazil, Paraguay and the United States—, and *implementing* foreign solutions to specific problems, where “implementing” is used in the sense of applying a solution to a problem that might have required another.

In addition to this problem, as many other countries, Uruguay has not yet developed a culture of investing resources in maintaining structures and civil infrastructure. A well known work by De Sitter [4] shows that the costs required to guarantee the durability of a concrete structure increase sharply as the aging process progresses. Although this research was developed for reinforced concrete and does not contemplate the financial costs of spending before [5], it clearly supports the popular wisdom that prevention is better than cure. The lack of maintenance of Uruguayan timber structures has led to the development of assorted problems related to high moisture content.

1.1 Case study

This article presents the work of inspection, characterization and structural analysis carried out in a timber structure in Uruguay. The structure, shown in Figure 1, consist in the gable roof of a warehouse, built at the beginning of the 20th century. The existing fibre-cement roof covering rests on sawn timber purlins, which in turn discharge on Pratt trusses —made of sawn timber pieces joined by traditional woodworking joints. Each of the ten trusses, of 21.60 m of span, is separated 4.00 m from each other.

Two year ago, in 2017, the owners of the building contacted the Faculty of Engineering, *Universidad de la República*, to inspect the structure and to propose a rehabilitation project. This request arose because of two reasons: the roof had some leaks that allow rainwater to reach the timber structure; and the owners wanted to change the roof covering, to solve the problem of the leaks and to improve the thermal insulation of the enclosure. As background of the structure, the owner shared with us a geometric survey of the building, which includes the general dimensions of the roof trusses, but not the materials data or the details of the construction (*e.g.*, the design of the joints or the loads considered on the timber structure). This information is represented in Figure 2, which shows the location of the timber trusses in the building (labeled as T1 to T10), and the pieces that make up each of the trusses —where TC is top chord, BC is bottom chord, VB is vertical bar, DB is diagonal bar and ES is external strut.

Figure 1: Photograph of the existing timber structure

Figure 2: (a) Location of the timber trusses, labeled as T1 to T10; (b) denomination of the pieces that make up each one of the Pratt trusses

1.2 Objectives

Based on the concerns raised by the clients, the aim of the work was to evaluate the structural condition of the timber trusses of the warehouse. To fulfill this, we set three objectives: first, to inspect the trusses; second, to characterize the timber—since no technical records of the original project were founded—; and third, to analyze the structure with the new load configuration. This article presents the methodology and results of this research work.

2 METHODOLOGY

The followed methodology is divided in three parts: first, we inspected the trusses visually; second, we estimated the timber mechanical properties destructively (by longitudinal compression tests of small-scale wood specimens) and non-destructively (by wave propagation testing techniques); and finally, we modeled and analyzed the trusses, in both the ultimate and serviceability limit states, after placing the projected new covering.

2.1 Visual inspection

We visually inspected all the accessible trusses (particularly trusses T8 and T9) to measure the sections of the different elements (listed in Figure 2-b), and to detect the damage caused by biotic agents and propose adapted methods of restoration. As complement, we drilled certain points of the timber trusses to evaluate the rotting depth.

2.2 Characterization of the timber

2.2.1 Destructive characterization

We extracted a sample from a sawn timber element, in an area with no structural function and in a truss that will later be removed in the restoration work. Figure 3-a shows the process of cutting and extracting the sample, while Figure 3-b shows a detail of the cut sample. The sample was oven-dried, according to EN 13183-1 [6], to obtain the moisture content and the corrected density for a moisture content of 12 % (ρ).

The sample was also useful to cut two small-scale specimens (of 20x20x60 mm³), which we used to obtain the compressive modulus of elasticity in the direction of the grain ($E_{c,0}$) and the compressive strength. These tests were carried out in a hydraulic press following the recommendations of EN 408 [7] and UNE 56535 [8], as Figure 3-c shows. As also shown in Figure 3-c, the strains were measured by two strain gauges, struck on two opposite faces. The compressive modulus of Young (in the direction of the grain) allowed us to calculate the flexural modulus of elasticity (E_m) from Equations 1 and 2 [9].

$$E_m = \frac{4 E_{t,0} E_{c,0}}{(\sqrt{E_{t,0}} + \sqrt{E_{c,0}})^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{E_{t,0}}{E_{c,0}} = 1.2 \quad (2)$$

where $E_{t,0}$ is the tensile modulus of elasticity in the direction of the grain.

Figure 3: (a) Extraction of the sawn timber sample; (b) detail of the cut sample; (c) compression test of the small-scale wood specimen

2.2.2 Non-destructive characterization

The non-destructive characterization of the sawn timber started by measuring the moisture content on several points of the trusses. Figure 4-a shows the equipment used for this purpose: a GANN xylohygrometer, which allows to estimate the moisture content at a depth between 20 and 30 mm from the surface of the timber element.

We also measured the pulse velocity—in the direction parallel to the grain—in different zones of the structure, with a Fakopp *Microsecond-timer*. As Figure 4-b shows, this equipment consists of two piezoelectric sensors connected to a central processing unit. Initially, an operator nails the sensors at an arbitrary distance d . A hammer tap on the start sensor generates a stress wave, which propagates through the material at a velocity v . When the other sensor receives the signal, the unit displays the propagation time (t). Equation 3 relate these three magnitudes.

$$v = \frac{d}{t} \quad (3)$$

Figure 4: (a) Moisture content measurement with a GANN xylohygrometer; (b) pulse velocity measurement with a Fakopp *Microsecond-timer* equipment

The pulse velocity may be used to assess the level of wood decay. In addition, it allows to obtain the dynamic modulus of elasticity—in the direction parallel to the grain— (E_{dyn}), as Equation 4 states [10]. Since the dynamic modulus of elasticity—calculated from Equation 4—depends on the moisture content of the measured element, it should be adjusted to a moisture content of 12 % to correctly compare the results at different location points [11].

$$E_{dyn} = \rho \cdot v^2 \quad (4)$$

2.3 Structural analysis

The last step was to model the structure using the finite element method in the software for structural analysis and design SAP2000 v20 [12]. The trusses were modeled by means of frame elements, with the cross-sections measured during the visual inspection and considering an orthotropic material, of modulus of elasticity (in the direction parallel to the grain) and density equal to those obtained from the timber characterization. The remaining elastic properties were calculated as stipulated in standards EN 338 [13] and EN 384 [14].

Regarding the actions on the structure, we considered the gravity load of the timber elements and the projected roof covering, and the imposed load of a not accessible roof, except for normal maintenance and repair. Both dead and live loads were calculated according to EN 1991-1-1 [15]. Wind loads were obtained from standards UNIT 50 [16] and EN 1991-1-4 [17], considering four perpendicular wind directions. Based on the load combinations stated in EN 1990 [18], we finally analyzed and checked the trusses in both the ultimate and serviceability limit states, according to Eurocode 5 (EN 1995-1-1) [19].

3 RESULTS

3.1 Visual inspection

The main problem detected during the visual inspection was the decay of some elements of the trusses, particularly in the areas near the supports. Although in most of the points inspected the attacks were shallow and the advance of the rot had stopped, some of the encounters between the trusses and the masonry walls showed active attacks of fungal rot (brown rot). Figure 5 shows two examples of this problem, in which the extent of the damage reached the total thickness of the pieces. In these cases, we recommended the elimination of the damaged areas and the reinforcement of the corresponding joints.

We also detected that, in some areas, the trusses did not behave structurally as it had been designed. For example, Figure 6 shows two problems —a longitudinal crack in the bottom chord and a malfunctioning of the woodworking scarf joint— that may be associated with an excessive deformation of the king post (VB3), which subjects the bottom chord to bending.

Figure 5: (a) Presence of brown rot in the supports, particularly in the joint between the top and bottom chord; (b) cracking of a concrete column by the swelling of an external strut

Figure 6: Central and lower part of truss T5, which presents a longitudinal crack in the bottom chord, an excessive deformation of the king post (VB3), and a malfunctioning of the woodworking scarf joint

Table 1 shows the cross-sectional dimensions of the of the elements of the trusses. Due to the shallow decay of many of the structural elements, we considered —for the structural analysis— an “effective section”, which consists of reducing the dimensions of the cross section by a minimum of 6 mm, adjustable if the depth of rot was greater.

Table 1: Cross-sectional dimensions of the of the elements of the trusses

Element	Type	Section (mm x mm)
BC, TC1 and TC2	Simple	79 x 229
VB1 and VB5	Double	54 x 157
VB2 and VB4	Double	74 x 160
VB3	Simple	78 x 220
DB1 and DB4	Simple	87 x 159
DB2 and DB3	Simple	75 x 222
ES1 and ES2	Double	60 x 157

3.2 Characterization of the timber

The extracted sample had a moisture content of 9.4 % and a corrected density for a moisture content of 12 % equal to 610 kg/m^3 . Table 2 presents the results of the compressive tests of the small-scale specimens obtained from this sample —where F_R is the maximum compressive load and $f_{c,0}$ is the compressive strength in the direction parallel to the grain.

Table 2: Results of the compression tests of the small-scale specimens

Specimen	F_R (kN)	$f_{c,0}$ (MPa)	$E_{c,0}$ (GPa)
1	22.0	55.0	16.3
2	18.5	46.3	18.1
Average	20.3	50.6	17.2

If we enter the mean value of $E_{c,0}$ —presented in Table 2— in Equations 1 and 2, we get that the mean value of E_m (flexural modulus of elasticity) is equal to 18.8 GPa. In this same piece, the corrected pulse velocity resulted 5770 m/s; thus, inputting this velocity and the measured density in Equation 4, we obtained that E_{dyn} (dynamic modulus of elasticity) is equal to 20.3 GPa. From these two values, we obtained the relationship between the static (bending) and dynamic (longitudinal) modulus of elasticity, as Equation 5 presents.

$$E_m/E_{dyn} = 0.926 \quad (5)$$

This relationship allowed us to estimate the static modulus of elasticity (E_m) of the timber in all the areas in which we measured the pulse velocity and the moisture content. In this way, we estimated that the average value of E_m is 11.5 GPa. This value is lower than 18.8 GPa since, in most of these areas, the pulse velocity was lower than in the extracted sample.

Taking into account the distribution of the annual rings, the color of the wood, and species commonly commercialized at the time of the construction of the structure, we considered highly likely that the wood species belonged to the “Southern yellow pine” group, locally known as “Pino tea”. There are several species of the family *Pinaceae* that can be identified with this name, including longleaf pine (*Pinus palustris*), short-leaf pine (*Pinus echinata*), slash pine (*Pinus elliottii*) and loblolly pine (*Pinus taeda*) [20]. EN 1912 [21] —that lists the visual strength grades, species and sources of timber, and specifies the strength classes to which they are assigned— includes two visual grades of “Southern yellow pine”: “SS”, to which it assigns a C24 strength class; and “GS”, to which it assigns a C18 strength class.

Based on the obtained results, and restricting the possible strength classes to those two, we conclude that the timber can be graded as C24 (higher modulus of elasticity); thus, we use the corresponding properties for the structural analysis, with the exception of the density, which we consider according to the obtained value (610 kg/m^3).

3.3 Structural analysis

Figures 7 and 8 show the axial force diagrams of two load combinations: C1 and C2. These two load combinations are those that generate the maximum axial loads in all the elements of the trusses. A red shading expresses a compressive force, while a blue shading a tensile force.

Figure 7: Axial force diagram for the load combination C1

Figure 8: Axial force diagram for the load combination C2

These results show that the wind load —particularly the one generated by a wind of direction perpendicular to the plane of the trusses— is large enough to cause the forces in the elements to change sign according to the combination. This is a common situation in the design of warehouses in Uruguay, especially near the coastal strip. A priori, this effect was not considered in the original design of the trusses since the lower chord was not adequately braced and many of the joints were designed to support a single type of effort. For example, Figure 6 shows that the central diagonals (DB2 and DB3) are joined to the king post (VB3) by a woodworking joint that only resists compression forces. To solve this problem, we suggested redesigning all the joints that support a single type of effort.

With respect to the timber elements, although they seem to have been correctly designed for the axial forces, not so for the bending moments. This is particularly noticeable in the top chord, which receives the support reactions of the purlins and a large concentrated force produced by the external struts (ES1 and ES2). According to this result, we recommended removing the external struts —which also do not seem to be part of the original design— and supporting the new roof covering in purlins, which in turn discharge as close as possible to the nodes of the trusses. The new covering should be able to withstand the resulting spans.

Given that the design value of the effects of the actions is very close to the design value of the corresponding resistance in several elements —even having considered a strength class C24—, we recommended carrying out bending tests on samples of structural size. These tests, which can be performed at the beginning of the repair work, would make possible to verify that the timber actually has the mechanical properties obtained indirectly.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented an evaluation of the structural condition of the timber trusses —of the gable roof of a warehouse in Uruguay. This evaluation was divided into three parts: first, we inspected the trusses visually; second, we characterized the timber with both destructive and non-destructive testing techniques; and third, we modeled, analyzed and verified the trusses with the new load configuration.

In the visual inspection we detected that some of the encounters between the trusses and the masonry walls showed active attacks of fungal rot (brown rot); therefore, we recommended the elimination of the damaged areas and the reinforcement of the corresponding joints. Based on the destructive and non-destructive tests, we estimated the mechanical properties of the timber to be those of a C24 strength class —though denser (610 kg/m³). The structural analysis of the trusses showed that the new roof covering (new loads configuration) and the stresses fluctuation due to suction wind could critically affect the structural behavior of both the woodworking joints and the trusses elements. To solve these problems, we suggested redesigning all the joints that support a single type of effort and changing the support and load configuration to reduce the bending moments in some timber elements.

This structure is an example of two local practices common in the past —product of the lack of knowledge of Uruguayan timber designers—: importing timber from other countries and *implementing* —without a planned adaptation— foreign solutions to specific problems. The latter is particularly noticeable in the design of the joints: while the original design works well for downward roof loads, it does not in places where fierce winds can generate a change in the sign of the stresses. This case study also shows the importance of investing resources in maintaining structures. If the water leaks had been detected and corrected in time, the timber would not have experienced decay. The costs of repairing all the areas affected today clearly exceed what it would have cost to control the state of the structure and repair it on time.

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